

Instructions for Joystick coding (20.08.2024)

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Content instructions and guidelines

1. Focus on rating the features of the language learners' interactional behaviour: dominance and affiliation. Do not assess their language skills, such as their proficiency level (this will be assessed separately).
2. Rate the individuals as individuals, focus your attention on the participant being rated.
3. Focus on observable features: base your ratings on what can be seen and heard.
4. Rate the participants by interpreting their nonverbal and verbal features together as a whole. Try to evaluate the situation comprehensively, considering all observable features. Do not focus only on certain features, for example, eye contact on its own does not correlate with high dominance or momentary leaning back should not be interpreted as withdrawing from the interaction completely.
5. People can intuitively understand other people, so trust yourself as a rater.
6. Use the primary labels for the x and y-axes: dominant/submissive, friendly/unfriendly. (Even though the octants were labelled more specifically during the practice phase.)
7. Try to utilize the entire scale when rating. (Although in our data the participants probably do not show strong distress or aggressiveness.) Do not feel afraid to code extremes. For instance, friendliness can be coded to be maximum if the participant is, smiling, joking or laughing and supporting the conversation in a friendly manner.
8. If there is a pause in the video where the participants are not interacting, speaking or gesturing, stop the rating by moving the joystick to the middle of the cartesian plane (0, 0). A pause of this kind is, for example, going to the toilet, an interruption by the researcher or a participant reading the exercise quietly to themselves. Other short pauses are a normal part of the dialogue but should be interpreted as reducing the participant's dominance.
9. In the role-playing exercises, rate what can be seen and heard, even if the dialogue is "acted out". For instance, if the participant is not actually angry but acts angry for the exercise, interpret their behaviour as angry.
10. Note down interesting observations in the data collection spreadsheet. Report them in team meetings or after the ratings are completed.
11. Joystick-coding is cognitively demanding and requires alertness. Take a short break in between each rating. Take a longer break after having coded around 20 minutes of videos (first finish rating each video in their entirety).

12. Do the ratings independently, do not discuss them with the other rater (except technical problem-solving is allowed). Discussion is also allowed at the halfway checkpoint when assuring the quality of the ratings. If you need help during the coding process, read pp. 31–32 in the Joystick Manual (“Issues Trainees may have with Joystick Coding”) or contact your supervisor.

Technical instructions

13. Download the video on to your computer locally.
14. Always watch the video through once before coding, so that you understand the context. (We noticed during practice that understanding the context is an important factor in interpreting the participants’ behaviour.) Focus on the participant that you will rate when watching the video.
15. Use a separate monitor. Set the media player window to be W39xH23.5 cm at the top left corner of the screen, and the JoyMon window to be W11xH13 cm. Set JoyMon to the bottom corner on the side of the participant that you are coding (participant on the right in the video = JoyMon on the bottom right corner of the screen).
16. Configure the Joymon settings as in Picture 1 below.
 - a. Name the file with this convention before you start rating:
date_speakerAspeakerB_task_targetspeaker_rater_rating, for example
20240613_speaker001speaker002_task5_speaker001_nn_001
17. To start rating: Start the video from the very beginning and the JoyMon rating (press button 3) at the same time. Press button 1 on the joystick to mark when the actual performance starts and ends.
18. Stop the JoyMon rating by pressing button 3 twice.
19. Add “.csv” to the end of the file name and delete the added 000 from end of the file name.
20. Move the files to the folder assigned to the rater.
21. Rate the videos according to the order on the list provided by your supervisor.
22. If you encounter technical problems with the videos, skip over the video without watching it and make a note of the problem.

Picture 1: JoyMon settings